

FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association (FAIR WISH)

D12: Summary on the Potential of IGSNs and User Requirements in the Domains of Earth System Science and beyond (AWI, GFZ)

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of this Document

This document contains deliverable D12 *Summary on the Potential of IGSNs and User Requirements in the Domains of Earth System Science and beyond* of the project **FAIR Workflows** to establish IGSN for **Samples** in the **Helmholtz Association (FAIR WISH)** funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC). The aim of this document is to provide background, perspectives and lessons learned during FAIR WISH on the potential, opportunities, and challenges of introducing the International Generic Sample Number (IGSN, www.igsn.org) to physical samples of the domains of Earth System Science and beyond, specifically targeting the research field Earth and Environment of the German Helmholtz Centres.

1.2 The Role of Samples and IGSNs for Open Science

While the Berlin Declaration from 2003 was the starting point for Open Access to scholarly publications, Open Science today reaches far beyond and represents collaborative, transparent and accessible research that includes all kinds of research results: scholarly literature, research data, software, samples, instruments, etc. In the FAIR WISH project, we focus on physical samples/ specimen, as they play a crucial role in the data life cycle, especially in the Earth and Environmental sciences (EaE). Samples record unique events in history (e.g., the meteorite impact that marks the geological boundary between the Cretaceous and the Tertiary and caused the extinction of the dinosaurs) and are often not reproducible. At the same time, samples are essential for reproducing and verifying research results and deriving new results by analysing existing samples with new methodology. Consequently, the inclusion of sample metadata in the digital data curation processes is an important step to provide the full provenance of research results.

The International Generic Sample Number (IGSN, www.igsn.org) is a globally unique, resolving, and persistent identifier (PID) for physical samples/specimens with a dedicated metadata schema supporting discovery functionality in the internet. IGSNs enable to directly link data and publications with the samples they originate from and inform about the whereabouts of a specific sample. IGSN is governed by an international non-profit organisation (IGSN e.V.) which also operated the central registration system based on the Handle.Net system until December 2022. Until then, IGSNs resolved via a persistent link to IGSN landing pages with a digital sample description, managed by federated IGSN allocating agents (e.g., <https://igsn.org/ICDP5054EHW1001>). GFZ is a founding member of IGSN e.V., and has been an active IGSN allocating agent for, e.g., samples of scientific drilling projects in the framework of the International Continental Scientific Drilling Program (ICDP) since 2015 (Conze et al., 2017). The IGSN metadata schema of GFZ was initially

aligned with that already in use by the System for Earth Sample Registration (SESAR, www.geosamples.org), the largest IGSN registering agency, and was only extended for specific cases, like, e.g., drilling methods. For later projects, some new metadata elements were added when required. The aim for this strategy was to be as harmonised as possible across IGSN allocating agents and facilitate search options in the planned global IGSN catalogue. The IGSN metadata schema is described in more detail in the following subsection.

1.3 IGSN Metadata

Until 2022, IGSNs were centrally registered as Handle PIDs by few international allocating agents, using the modular IGSN schema with the mandatory IGSN registration schema, the IGSN description Schema and additional specific extensions for specific sample types or sub-disciplines (Klump et al., 2021). This modular and very flexible approach is delineated in Figure 1: The IGSN registration schema is the central core for all IGSNs and contains only four mandatory elements common to all IGSNs - the identifier, a registrant, related identifiers and a log / timestamp. The IGSN description schema was designed as central descriptive metadata enabling data discovery. It was not mandatory across IGSN e.V. allocating agents, but strongly recommended for discovery and for building a central sample catalogue, as it included many relevant metadata properties that could be provided for most samples (e.g. the name of the sample, the sample collector, the material, and a location).

GFZ uses the IGSN description schema (central dark blue sphere in Figure 1) and builds upon it with further GFZ specific elements (outer blue spheres in Figure 1). The GFZ specific elements currently contain 82 metadata properties and sub-properties that can be optionally filled (GFZ specific description schema).

Optional sample-type-specific metadata for additional geo-bio sample types were developed within the FAIR WISH project, and added to the GFZ specific metadata (green, grey, orange and yellow spheres representing vegetation, sediment, water and rock samples in Figure 1). These updated spheres specifically include further developed controlled lists of vocabularies (SKOS/RDF) for biological samples (GFBIO (Kamar et al., 2014), EnvO (Buttigieg et al., 2016), BTO (Chang et al., 2021)). We furthermore included vocabularies to describe the Biome (Olson et al., 2001) where from a sample was derived, elaborated the vocabularies for describing the landform (EnvO) and agreed on using IUGS-CGI's Simple Lithology for the specific description of rock samples.

Figure 1 IGSN description metadata schema, including proposed sample-type-specific metadata of the FAIR WISH project. GFZ specific descriptive metadata (blue spheres) built upon the IGSN central description schema (central dark blue sphere). Sample-type-specific metadata for further geo-bio sample types (green, grey, orange and yellow spheres representing vegetation, sediment and water samples) added to the GFZ specific metadata.

1.4 The IGSN DataCite Partnership

In October 2021, the IGSN e.V. and DataCite announced their strategic partnership (Buys and Lehnert, 2021). This induced a major change in the registration of IGSNs as they have to be registered as DataCite DOIs (IGSN IDs) since January 2023. The registration of IGSN Handle PIDs was only possible until December 2022 and all >10 Million registered IGSNs had to be reregistered as DataCite DOIs in Q1 of 2023 and their metadata partly mapped to the DataCite Schema following the agreed recommendations between the IGSN DataCite Partnership Steering Group (<https://support.datacite.org/docs/igsn-id-Metadata-recommendations>).

The merge of DataCite and IGSN also led to a situation, where all DataCite members can register samples without the central governing institution IGSN e.V. and by only the DataCite Mandatory properties (Identifier, Creator, Title, Publisher, PublicationYear, ResourceType and resourceTypeGeneral). Due to the transition, the cost model of IGSN also changed and the registration of IGSN DOIs follows the DataCite fee model (<https://datacite.org/feemodel.html>). As a member of the IGSN DataCite Partnership Steering Group, FAIR WISH PI Kirsten Elger actively participates in these discussions, especially in the metadata mapping group and directly bridges the FAIR WISH project activities with the international development of IGSN.

The comparison of the metadata schemas of IGSN and DataCite reveals their different purpose: The highly granular IGSN metadata was developed for the detailed description of different kinds of physical samples and their provenance (geo-bio samples in FAIR WISH, but IGSN would also be adoptable to describe, e.g.,

archaeological artefacts, synthetic samples). With the IGSN metadata, samples can be found in sample catalogues and people can identify whether a sample would be suitable for their scientific question. The DataCite metadata, on the other hand, is designed to provide bibliographic information for citation and supports data discovery across all science disciplines. It will never be able to fully replace the detailed description of samples from the IGSN metadata schema and is not intended to do so either. Therefore, GFZ Data Services, as IGSN agent, will further use the detailed IGSN metadata schema on their IGSN landing pages and sample catalogue. For the registration of IGSN IDs (DOIs) via DataCite, standard mapping scripts have been developed and applied within FAIR WISH (FAIR WISH D8).

2. Application of IGSN in FAIR WISH

Within the FAIR WISH project, (i) standardised, rich and discipline-specific IGSN metadata schemes for different physical sample types within EaE (FAIR WISH D1, D2, D3, D4) and (ii) workflows to generate machine-readable IGSN metadata from different states of digitisation were developed (FAIR WISH D2, D4, D5, D7, D8). These range from individual sample collections of scientists (Use Case AWI: samples from Russian-German expeditions, metadata from field books, data rescue project) to sample descriptions managed in digital sample management systems (Use Case GFZ: samples from drilling projects, metadata from mDIS - the mobile Drilling Information System (Behrends et al., 2020); Use Case Hereon: coastal and marine samples, metadata from the Hereon Expedition Database fed by a field app). During the project, a total of 14,596 IGSNs (for all three FAIR WISH use cases) have been registered as Handle IGSN and re-registered as DataCite IGSN IDs (DOIs) (FAIR WISH D6, D9, D10, D11). The metadata was collected with the FAIR SAMPLES Template (FAIR WISH D2, D3, D4), either by manual entry or by automated filling of the template as database export from digital sample management systems. For the automated IGSN metadata generation (XML) and registration, the SAMIRA software was developed as FAIR WISH D8 (Frenzel 2023).

2.1 FAIR SAMPLES Template in FAIR WISH

The FAIR SAMPLES Template (FAIR WISH D1, D2, D3, D4), developed based on Excel, provides users, specifically users with individual sample collections (constituting a large share in EaE communities) an easy and flexible way to assemble the metadata of their samples independent of the sample's level of digitalization and the training of the users. In addition, the FAIR SAMPLES Template can also be used for automated generation of IGSN metadata managed in databases (FAIR WISH D5, D7).

The FAIR SAMPLES Template can be used as a guideline, especially for the integration of controlled and linked-data vocabularies (SKOS/ RDF). Linked-data vocabularies are essential for the creation of ontologies as they enable interlinking and

comparing sample metadata in machine-actionable and interoperable form. To further enrich sample metadata description, we extended the IGSN controlled vocabularies to better describe samples outside the solid earth geoscience domains, so that now also water or vegetation samples can be well described (FAIR WISH D1).

The first version of a standardised, flexible and customisable metadata template for Geo-Bio samples (in short 'FAIR SAMPLES Template', FAIR WISH D2) contained all the required metadata elements for rich sample descriptions of different sample types relevant in the FAIR WISH context. Already at this stage, the modular template was developed as an all-in-one solution for the different use cases, with the ability for users to select only the variables needed for their specific sample type. The FAIR SAMPLES Template was distributed to several user communities in EaE and was successfully used for batch uploading of sample metadata to the GFZ IGSN Server for all use cases (FAIR WISH D6, D9, D10, D11).

FAIR WISH D3 provides a video tutorial with complementary visual and audio content on how to use the 'FAIR SAMPLES Template'. It also contains a usability questionnaire for receiving feedback on the application of the template. The feedback based on these usability questionnaires and activities such as one-to-one interviews forms the main feedback for evaluating the usability of the FAIR SAMPLES Template improving its applicability.

We optimised the FAIR SAMPLES Template based on multiple users' feedback from several domains of EaE and are providing version 2.0 of the FAIR SAMPLES Template including a ChangeLog (FAIR WISH D4), which describes the changes that have been made between the prototype described in D2, version v.1.0 published on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7520016>), as well as the changes between versions 1.0 and 2.0.

The FAIR SAMPLES Template v.2.0 provides multiple worksheets:

- i) the "HowTo" section, explaining how to use the Template
- ii) the "Guide" is the core worksheet of the FAIR SAMPLES template and used to select variables needed for sample description at four hierarchy levels and thus creating flexible template description sheets based on personal needs. The "Guide" provides the overview of the full metadata schema including definitions and examples to describe a sample. The modular internal organisation of the "Guide" is stratified into six main topics containing 87 variables in total. The modules thematically bundle variables that are linked to the topics Sample, Sampling, Location, Persons/ Institutes, Archive, and Reference (see also Table 1).
- iii-vi) the Templates itself at four hierarchy levels (Parent + Children 1, 2 and 3) in which only the selected variables from the modular six topics are shown and active and can then be filled with metadata by the user.

All following spreadsheets are providing the controlled vocabulary to be used in different metadata fields. The column “Content” in the “Guide” spreadsheet include links to these lists.

Table 1 FAIR SAMPLES template modular internal organisation with six topics, and numbers of topic-specific variables.

TOPIC	Sample	Sampling	Location	Persons/ Institutions	Archive	Reference
N variables	22	18	26	13	5	3

2.2 IGSN Registration in FAIR WISH

Use Case AWI: Sample field notes from Russian-German Expeditions (FAIR WISH D9)

Within the Use Case AWI, we could use the FAIR SAMPLES Template to fill it with the wide range of sample metadata properties provided. We optimised the templates for applications with hierarchical links of sample objects that all get assigned with IGSN. This refers to all typically occurring terrestrial samples from Russian-German long-term land expeditions to Siberia. It includes the extensively performed sampling in lakes (aquatic samples, sediment samples, sediment cores), and on vegetation plots (diverse biotic samples in different hierarchies, e.g., needle samples for DNA-analyses, as well as the parent-trees that were sampled and the parent-vegetation plots), or soil samples related to parent-soil pits related to parent-vegetation subplots.

We registered 1,636 IGSNs in different interlinked hierarchies for a wide range of aquatic, vegetation and soil samples from these past Russian-German expeditions as a very successful data rescue programme. The sample metadata were mainly created from existing field notes (field book, photo archive) and had only partly or not been digitised before.

The highly individual sampling on land expeditions in remote polar regions has so far not fully reached standardisation. AWI is developing various field apps (first versions served the MOSAiC expedition) for a range of user communities. However, specifically sample metadata from former expeditions in the terrestrial communities are not standardised at all yet. For these cases, the FAIR SAMPLES Template serves as a standardised description of sample metadata and will be further used to support the preparation of older and new expedition data for data publications thereby reducing duplication of work.

Specifically within FAIR WISH, 656 Siberian high latitude lakes, where the samples from the Russian-German expeditions originate from, have been assigned with IGSNs to make them unique as these lakes are usually lacking official names and geographical data descriptions. These lakes were organised as individual “datacentre”

within the GFZ Sample Catalogue (“High Latitude Lakes”). This IGSN assignment of high-latitude lakes and their identification as sampling features representing the upper-most hierarchy in sample trees is similar to the concept of the IGSN for boreholes representing the overall parent for a drilling project. The IGSN assignment together with the provision of rich IGSN metadata to so far officially unnamed lakes is politically endorsed by the pan-Arctic, land-based program Terrestrial Multidisciplinary distributed Observatories for the Study of Arctic Connections (T-MOSAiC, <https://www.t-mosaic.com/>) of the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC). The IGSNs of the Use Case AWI can be found in the IGSN GFZ Data Services catalogue at <https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/igsn-new/> by filtering for the datacenters “AWI Polar Terrestrial Environmental Ecosystems” and “High Latitude Lakes”.

Use Case GFZ: scientific drilling project Adlershof/ mDIS - mobile Drilling Information System (FAIR WISH D10)

The IGSN DataCite Partnership had a large impact on the FAIR WISH team at GFZ. GFZ has hosted the central IGSN Handle Server since 2012 and managed all IGSN prefixes for the more than 10 Million IGSN registered by 10 international IGSN allocating agents. During the transition process, some allocating agents were supported by GFZ and all >35,000 registered samples of the allocating agent GFZ had to be re-registered as DataCite DOIs after the mapping of IGSN metadata to the DataCite schema (see section 1.4). We therefore decided to change the GFZ Use Case from Ketzin to the timely more pressing scientific drilling project Adlershof (Norden et al., 2023).

The process that was applied to generate IGSN metadata was identical for both projects, Ketzin and Adlershof: rich sample metadata was already captured in the mobile Drilling Information System mDIS (Behrends et al., 2020) and from there semi-automatically exported and integrated in the FAIR SAMPLES Template. After data curation by the FAIR WISH team, the IGSN XML metadata were generated and the IGSNs were registered using the SAMIRA Software (FAIR WISH D8).

As GFZ Data Services developed the strategy for officially unnamed lakes specifically to accommodate T-MOSAiC (IASC) requirements, they will continue the assignment of IGSNs to high latitude lake objects (Arctic, Subarctic and Antarctica) starting with filled FAIR SAMPLES Templates from users from the Universities Laval, Canada, and Montpellier, France. The IGSNs of the lake objects can be found in future in the GFZ Sample Catalogue, datacentre “High Latitude Lakes”.

Use Case Hereon / Hereon Expedition Database (FAIR WISH D11)

The Use Case Hereon used the Hereon Expedition Database characterised by already highly standardised sample metadata because it is automatically fed by a field app. The Hereon Expedition Database has been developed since 2016 within the coastMap project (Baldewein et al., 2018). Its aim is to allow querying and downloading of

campaign data collected during ship and land-based sampling campaigns at the Hereon Institute of Carbon Cycles and Hereon Institute of Coastal Environmental Chemistry. The Use Case Hereon filled the FAIR SAMPLES Template directly from the database by code. The output of FAIR WISH D5 is a comma-separated file containing the FAIR SAMPLES Template metadata of 12,041 samples. Like this, in total 12,041 samples could be registered after converting the metadata (FAIR WISH D5, D6) by using the steps described in FAIR WISH D7. The IGSNs of the Use Case Hereon can be found in the IGSN GFZ Data Services catalogue at <https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/igsn-new/> by filtering for the datacentre “Expedition Database Hereon”.

Future IGSN Registration via FAIR SAMPLES Template

For future registration of IGSN, the template and metadata examples for specific samples is sent out to users, published via Zenodo and offered via the website of GFZ Data Services. The SAMIRA Software (FAIR WISH D8) supports the IGSN XML generation and registration.

3 User Feedback in FAIR WISH from the Research Field Earth and Environment

3.1. FAIR WISH Outreach Activities

Within FAIR WISH, we widely promoted the application of IGSN to enable sample metadata standardisation and sample registration with IGSNs. We introduced FAIR WISH within and beyond HMC activities at internal institute meetings as well as during international workshops and conferences (e.g. Baldewein et al., 2022).

To get detailed feedback on the FAIR SAMPLES Template, it was sent out to users at various institutes from a wide range of EaE and also to the PANGAEA® Data Publisher for EaE. The overall feedback on FAIR WISH, the application of IGSN and the FAIR SAMPLES Template was very positive. More feedback is expected and we will further inform on in the FAIR WISH final project report to be published in 2024. Overall, the majority of the optimisation process of the template was motivated by the immediate feedback of users. All changes are described in detail in a changelog document (FAIR WISH D4).

The display of all the connections between parent sample, children and siblings, e.g., as a visualisation of an IGSN sample tree in the GFZ data catalogue was very intriguing and convinced across the EaE user communities. Therefore, we are providing the

FAIR SAMPLES Template v. 2.0 with IGSN-specific parent-child hierarchies in different sheets. This way, it is technically possible to register parent samples and their children from one single template, thus connecting parent and children samples by the sample names. To explain the idea of sample hierarchies and how parents and children are connected, we are providing an information graph within the “HowTo” worksheet of the FAIR SAMPLES Template v. 2.0.

3.2. FAIR SAMPLES Template - Detailed User Feedback

We provide here the first detailed feedback from EaE user communities from four Helmholtz centres, two Universities, the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland and from the PANGAEA® Data Publisher for EaE (Table 2).

The overall feedback on the FAIR SAMPLES Template was very positive. Despite some users giving feedback that the template was overwhelming at a first glance, with the provided video tutorial and the flexibility of creating a template for one’s own needs, the user feedback was that it is a good experience. Overall, the provision of the video tutorial was highly appreciated.

It was noted in some cases, that it might be some work to “copy-paste” sample metadata from the user’s own digitised spreadsheet format into the template and that it might be useful in future to have a tool that automatically transfers data from one excel sheet into the FAIR SAMPLES Template. Specifically for cases, where only non-digitized field notes or only partly digitisation existed, the standardised description of sample metadata of the FAIR SAMPLES Template was highly appreciated and re-used in future by these users also for further purposes such as preparing the metadata for data publication projects.

The overall reception of the worksheet “GUIDE” was very positive. Only minor changes were asked for, such as changing the age unit from “ky BP” to “ka BP”, or automatically integrating a unit-field into the template, once a variable requiring a unit is selected. In a few cases, there were clarifications needed on the use of “other names” for the sample name. The difference between “Locality” and “Location” seems to be difficult to understand, however, this can be handled very individually by the users, accustomed to their needs. Users also requested to have restricted input in fields with controlled vocabularies. This user request proved challenging due to the avoidance of macros, restricted by many institutes, that we currently prioritise within FAIR WISH.

Currently, the field “biome” provides the internationally recognized 14 terrestrial biomes by Olson et al. (2001) as users of terrestrial samples requested it. In addition, users from marine samples are interested in a similar variable field providing the internationally recognized biogeochemical Longhurst provinces (associated with oceans and marine biomes, final version by Longhurst, 2007) that we plan to incorporate in a future version of the FAIR SAMPLES Template.

Table 2 User Feedback

User feedback	Research domains / Physical sample types
Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz-Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung (https://awi.de/)	terrestrial and marine bio-geoscience user communities / focus on aquatic, vegetation, soil, sediment core, snow, ground ice, and zoological samples
Helmholtz Center Hereon (https://www.hereon.de/)	marine and coastal bio-geoscience user communities / focus on aquatic, sediment, and sediment core samples
GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences (https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/)	solid earth geoscience user communities / focus on rock core and rock samples
GEOMAR Helmholtz-Zentrum für Ozeanforschung Kiel (https://www.geomar.de/)	marine bio-geoscience user communities / focus on zoological samples
PANGAEA (https://www.pangaea.de/)	Data Publisher for EaE
Georg-August Universität Göttingen (https://www.uni-goettingen.de/)	terrestrial geoscience user communities / focus on soil samples
Université de Montpellier, France (https://www.umontpellier.fr/)	terrestrial biogeoscience user communities / focus on aquatic samples
Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS) (https://pub.geus.dk/en/)	marine bio-geoscience user communities / focus on aquatic and sediment core samples

In the first version of the template, it was not clearly distinguished between sample types, material and the classifications of a material. Some essential terms were noted from users to be missing in the Material classification vocabularies. This was all solved in the new version of the FAIR SAMPLES Template v. 2.0.

4. Recommendations for the Research Field Earth and Environment and Beyond

Advancing understanding of the Earth System requires advanced digital scientific infrastructures. The internationally applied IGSN has the potential to play a crucial role due to its power of identifying, citing, and tracking scientific sample types across international scientific data and text publications.

Historical and long-term environmental datasets are the tools to disentangle how our changing world responds to changing conditions. The Earth System Science concept described in the Helmholtz Program of Changing Earth, Research Field EaE (Helmholtz Changing Earth Program board, 2018), provides the currently needed comprehensive framework for interdisciplinary science application. Much of the

required data to understand the state of the Earth and its change is derived from scientific sampling in the Earth system spheres that are represented by the Geosphere, Hydrosphere, including the Cryosphere, Atmosphere, Biosphere, and Anthroposphere all interconnected through material and energy fluxes. Figure 2 displays the IGSN and its potential to cover the requirements for FAIR samples in the Helmholtz Program of Changing Earth, Research Field EaE.

Figure 2: The IGSN has the potential to cover the requirements for FAIR samples in EaE. - We developed rich and discipline-specific IGSN metadata schemes and workflows for a wide range of sample types that potentially be collected in the several Earth System spheres Hydrosphere, Cryosphere, Biosphere and Geosphere. Within FAIR WISH, we could register IGSNs already for the majority of spheres, highlighted with “IGSN” (Figure adapted after *Changing Earth - Sustaining our Future*, Research Field EaE, 2018). Potentially, IGSNs could also be used for samples in the Anthroposphere and Atmosphere spheres, e.g. for archaeological samples.

With the partnership of IGSN e.V. and DataCite starting in the beginning of 2023, IGSN changed from being a handle registered at specific allocating agents to a DOI which can be registered by any DataCite member or consortium member. As DataCite mandatory variables are valuable, but not intended to describe physical sample objects and therefore not sufficient for this application, it is important to keep with the established IGSN metadata structure, providing it in a user friendly format.

Within the FAIR WISH project, we developed standardised, rich and discipline-specific IGSN metadata schemes for different physical sample types supported by the FAIR SAMPLES Template and workflows to generate machine-readable IGSN metadata

from different states of digitisation. The generation of IGSN XML metadata files and their registration was supported by the in-house developed SAMIRA software.

The FAIR SAMPLES Template enables batch upload of samples at various sample hierarchies (parent, children at different hierarchy levels) at once, without having to IGSN-register the parent objects before. The opportunity to fill the FAIR SAMPLES Template by individual researchers or research teams (mostly from long-tail communities) or to create scripts to fill it out directly from databases for a very wide range of sample types makes the template flexible with a wide applicability. The process, however, is not fully automated yet. Especially the manual provision of terms from lists in different sheets of the template (copy and paste) is error prone and requires an increased data curation workload that is not scalable at the long term. The structured metadata, captured with the FAIR SAMPLES Template and converted into XML files, already represents an important step for the standardisation of rich sample descriptions in machine-readable way that is outweighing the disadvantages described above.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

The main change of the IGSN DataCite Partnership was the technical change of PID from Handles to DataCite DOIs. In addition, all DataCite members can now register samples without the central governing institution IGSN e.V. and by only providing the DataCite mandatory metadata properties (Identifier, Creator, Title, Publisher, PublicationYear, ResourceType and resourceTypeGeneral). The latter has a high potential for losing the previous joint effort coordinated by IGSN e.V. DataCite's mandatory variables are valuable, but not intended to describe physical sample objects and therefore not sufficient for this application. Allocating agents and repositories are still not fully aware of the potential of the DataCite metadata schema and often only provide the mandatory properties for DOI registration, while capturing much more metadata within their own implementations.

The possibility to assign PIDs to physical objects/ specimen and the IGSN is increasingly observed beyond EaE. Scientific disciplines, like archaeology, are current exploring to use IGSNs for their artefacts and form a new a “community of practice” (<https://scaledagileframework.com/communities-of-practice/>). This would certainly strengthen the relevance of IGSN, but will put additional challenges on the IGSN metadata. How much of the “common kernel” agreed within the EaE (Figure 1) can be applied for archaeological samples and will it ever be possible to create a global sample catalogue?

Many people and institutes across the different domains of EaE are interested in using the IGSN as FAIR documentations of their samples. Therefore, it is important to keep with the established IGSN metadata structure, providing it in a user-friendly format. The FAIR SAMPLES Template and developed workflows in FAIR WISH are in such

user friendly formats, fully applicable for sample description and for scalable FAIR sample metadata publications. The FAIR SAMPLES Template is on the one hand flexible and easy-to use, and on the other hand extensive enough to describe a variety of sample types.

We will apply in the next HMC call for a follow-up project, FAIR AIMS, which, in case of successful financing, shall enhance user experience by creating a web application with modules including (i) a Guided Sample Template generation optimised for different sample types, (ii) an online upload of populated Sample Templates with quality assurance, and (iii) Dynamical web forms for single sample submissions. They shall ensure a user-friendly and at the same time high-quality metadata submission.

List of FAIR WISH Deliverables

FAIR WISH D1

Baldewein, L., Brauser, A., Elger, K., Heim, B., & Wieczorek, M. (2022). FAIR WISH D1 - List of identified linked open data vocabularies to be included in IGSN metadata. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6787199>

FAIR WISH D2

Wieczorek, M., Heim, B., Brauser, A., Elger, K., & Baldewein, L. (2022). FAIR WISH D2 - Exemplary standardised metadata templates for Geo-Bio samples (vegetation, water, sediment, rock samples) for all use cases. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7147531>

FAIR WISH D3

Wieczorek, M., Heim, B., Brauser, A., Elger, K., & Baldewein, L. (2022). FAIR WISH D3 - Assisting and Assessing User application of the FAIR SAMPLES Template. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377903>

Wieczorek, M., Brauser, A., Heim, B., Baldewein, L., & Elger, K. (2022). Video Tutorial for the FAIR SAMPLES Template. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7381389>

FAIR WISH D4

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FAIR WISH D8

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These deliverables were not accompanied by a report, as they are the registration of IGSNs. They have been preponed to months 12 (from month 24) as a consequence of the IGSN DataCite Partnership. All registered samples can be found in the IGSN Catalogue of GFZ Data Services (<https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/igsn-new/>) as the following Datacenters: AWI Polar Terrestrial Environmental Systems; Expedition database Hereon, GFZ Potsdam, High Latitude Lakes.

FAIR WISH D12

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8. List of Acronyms/ Glossary

ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons (https://ardc.edu.au/)
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institut Helmholtz Zentrum für Polar- und Meeresforschung (https://awi.de)
EaE	Earth and Environment: one of six research fields of the Helmholtz Association of German Research Centres (https://www.helmholtz.de/en/)
EnvO	EnvO, the Environmental Ontology, is a community ontology for the concise, controlled description of environments (https://sites.google.com/site/environmentontology/)
FAIR	FAIR Guiding Principles for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable research data (Wilkinson et al., 2015)
FAIR WISH	FAIR Workflows to establish IGSN for Samples in the Helmholtz Association (https://helmholtz-metadaten.de/en/inf-projects/fair-wish-fair-workflows-to-establish-igsn-for-samples-in-the-helmholtz-association)
GEOMAR	GEOMAR Helmholtz-Zentrum für Ozeanforschung Kiel (https://www.geomar.de/)
GFBIO	German Federation for Biological Data (https://www.gfbio.org/)
GFZ	GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences (https://www.gfz-potsdam.de/)
Hereon	Helmholtz Center Hereon (https://www.hereon.de/)
HMC	Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration: one of the Helmholtz Information & Data Science Incubators, HMC promotes the qualitative enrichment of research data by means of metadata – and implements this approach across the whole organisation (https://helmholtz-metadaten.de/en)
IGSN	International Generic Sample Number (https://www.igsn.org/)
ITIS	Integrated Taxonomic Information System: Authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes of North America and the world. (https://www.itis.gov/ ; USGS 2013)
IUGS-CGI	IUGS-CGI: Commission for the Management and Application of Geoscience Information (CGI) under the International Union for Geological Sciences (IUGS)
mDIS	mobile Drilling Information System is a data entry system for geological samples and drilling engineering data, developed by the International Continental Scientific Drilling Programme (ICDP, https://data.icdp-online.org/mdis-docs/)

ODM2	Observations Data Model 2, An information model and supporting software ecosystem for feature-based Earth observations (https://www.odm2.org/)
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDF	Resource Description Format: RDF is a standard model for data interchange on the Web. RDF has features that facilitate data merging even if the underlying schemas differ, and it specifically supports the evolution of schemas over time without requiring all the data consumers to be changed. RDF extends the linking structure of the Web to use URIs to name the relationship between things as well as the two ends of the link (this is usually referred to as a “triple”). Using this simple model, it allows structured and semi-structured data to be mixed, exposed, and shared across different applications (https://www.w3.org/RDF/)
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier